

Comparative Prospective Analysis of Intra-Articular Fracture of Proximal Tibia Managed by Joshi's External Stabilizing System (JESS) Versus Plate Fixation**Vaibhav Adhulia¹, Chandra Shekhar Verma², Saurabh Singh³, Rohit Patel⁴, Dibya Singh⁵, Lawanya Verma⁶, Divya Verma⁷**^{1,2,3,4}Assistant Professor, Department Of Orthopaedics G.S.V.M. Medical Collage Kanpur⁵Associate Professor, Department of Obs & Gynae, Saraswati Medical Collage Unnao⁶Senior Resident, Department Of Pathology, King George Medical University, Lucknow⁷Junior Resident, Department Of Pathology, UCMS & GTB Hospital Delhi

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Rohit Patel

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Among various treatment options available at present for tibial plateau fractures, Joshi's external stabilization system (JESS) is one of the established modalities for external fixation. While open reduction and plate fixation gives better reduction of articular fragments, closed reduction and JESS fixation has advantage of soft tissue preservation and early initiation of rehabilitation.**Objective:** Main purpose of this study was to compare the functional outcome between plate and JESS fixation method. Design: This was a comparative prospective analysis nonrandomized study.**Materials and Methods:** Among total enrolled 33 patients, 10 and 23 patients were treated by JESS and Plating methods respectively. Modified Rasmussen functional score (MRFS) was used for assessing the patients at each follow up. Statistical analysis was done by Microsoft excel and statistical software SPSS 21. Student t- test was applied to find if difference was significant between the groups.**Results:** In the study majority of the patients were between 20-30 years (mean 35.72 years) of age. Males were affected more than females, road traffic accident was the main cause (84.84% cases). There were 23 closed and 10 open fracture cases. Of the total, 60% cases were schatzker's type VI and 18.18% were schatzker's type V. The follow-up period was 6 months. On comparative analysis of the two groups at 2 weeks and 6 weeks, there was significant relationship at p value<0.001. At the period of 3 month and 6 months, both the groups are equally effective and there was non-significant relationship at the p value of >0.05. While at the latest follow-up, both the groups were significant at p value of <0.001.**Conclusion:** The study shows that the functional outcome of plating for the management of tibial plateau fractures is better than JESS.**Keywords:** Tibial Plateau Fracture, JESS, Plating, Rasmussen's Score.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

All the fractures around the knee joint, are of paramount importance as would result in significant morbidity and deterioration in quality of life. Intra-articular proximal tibia fractures, i.e., tibial plateau fractures, account for almost 1% of all fractures and usually result from axial loading combined with some varus and valgus forces. [1]

Presently, most of the proximal tibia fractures occur in productive age group (20-40 years) secondary to high-speed motor vehicle accidents and fall from height.

Till date, a common treatment protocol for each type of complex tibial plateau fractures has not developed. Conservative management via plaster

cast immobilization has major limitation of inadequate reduction of the articular surface and ineffective limb alignment control. [2] External fixation using closed method for reduction of fracture promote early mobilization thereby decreasing the hospital stay, but closed treatment has little success in reducing depressed and displaced fracture fragments. This necessitates open treatment in most displaced and unstable fractures. In open fixation methods, intra-articular alignment is obtained by elevation of depressed articular fragment and fixation with plates and screws. Present study was conducted to assess outcome of proximal tibia fractures managed by

JESS compared to proximal tibia plating in terms of functional result.

Material and Methods

This study was carried out in the Department of Orthopaedics, L.L.R. and associated hospitals, G.S.V.M. Medical College, Kanpur. It was a prospective comparative study conducted between December 2019 to October 2021.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients having proximal tibia fractures of <3 weeks duration including tibial plateau fractures of either sex, fractures of < grade 3b Gustilo-Anderson classification with intact neurovascular status, skeletally mature individuals (>18 years age) who gave consent for intervention and willing to come for regular follow-up were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with injury of >3 weeks duration fractures of grade 3c Gustilo-Anderson classification, unfit for surgery and having pathological fracture were excluded from study.

Method: On arrival of patient in casualty / out-patient department informed consent was taken according to guidelines of institutional ethical committee. Prior to starting of study approval from institutional ethical committee was taken.

After detailed history and clinical examination patients were investigated clinically, haematologically, and a thorough pre-anaesthetic check-up was done. Radiographs of affected tibia in AP and lateral views were taken. CT scans done in doubtful articular depression fractures. Fractures were classified according to schatzker's classification. Supportive measures in the form of immobilization, knee aspiration to relieve hemarthrosis, limb elevation and others were used in preoperative period.

Operative management: fractures with compound were serially debrided as per requirement before definitive surgical management, autologous bone graft was used from iliac crest in required cases. Surgical technique of JESS: Under the guidance of image intensifier reduction of comminuted fragments done using principle of ligamentotaxis, articular incongruity >3mm indicated open reduction with limited incision. After acceptable reduction, K- wires of 2-3 mm and 6.5 mm cancellous cannulated screws were placed in juxta-articular bone to maintain reduction. In next step 3 K-wires (2.5mm) inserted in juxta-articular bone parallel to articular surface at different angles and 3 K- wires (3mm) placed parallel to each other in distal tibia

fragment. Additional K- wires each in proximal and distal fragments were used to maintain mechanical axis and prevent rotation of fragments. Finally, all K- wires in proximal and distal fragments were connected to each other by JESS blocks and rods to make a stable JESS construct. Surgical technique of proximal tibia Plating: Articular displaced split fractures where possible were reduced indirectly by reduction forceps under image intensifier otherwise open reduction was performed. Subchondral screws using 3.5 mm cortical screws and temporary k-wires were placed to maintain reduction. An lateral curved incision was made from Gerdy's tubercle extending distally for about 5 c.m. to introduce locking plate submuscularly through anterolateral approach and position confirmed on image intensifier. Finally plate applied to bone on anterolateral aspect of bone through MIPPO (minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis) technique. Posteromedial plating in epiperiosteal plane was done in schatzker's type IV, V and VI where addition buttress was required.

Post-operative period: In post-operative period regular pin tract dressing in JESS group and appropriate antibiotics were used for both groups. Passive knee flexion exercises were started on next day of surgery. Active range of motion exercises at knee and static quadriceps exercise started on 3rd day in most patients as soon as pain was tolerable, followed by quadriceps strengthening exercises. Partial weight bearing was started at 8 to 10 weeks in both groups. Full weight bearing was allowed after clinical or radiological union.

Follow — up: PTB brace / support, sticks given depending on requirement of patients. JESS construct was removed after clinical or radiological union. The follow up was done at 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months for both groups. At each follow up assessment was done using modified Rasmussen's functional score. Progress and patient complaints were recorded in accordance using modified Rasmussen's functional score.

Statistical Analysis: Microsoft excel and statistical software SPSS 21 was used for the analysis of data. Student t- test was applied to find if difference was significant between the groups. P value of <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant in the study.

Observation and Results

Amongst the enrolled 33 patients, 10 and 23 patients were treated by JESS and Plating methods respectively.

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age (in years)	No. of cases	Percentage
20-30	14	42.42%
31-40	11	33.33%
41-50	04	12.12%
51-60	02	6.06%
61-70	02	6.06%
Total	33	

The study reveals that majority of the patients are between 20-30 years of age.

Table 2: Sex Distribution

Sex	No. of cases	Percentage
Male	29	87.8%
Female	4	12.2%
Total	33	

The study shows that males are affected more as compared to females.

Table 3: Mode of Injury

Mode of injury	No. of cases	Percentage
Road traffic accident	28	84.84%
Fall from height	03	9.09%
Assault	01	3.03%
Miscellaneous	01	3.03%
Total	33	

Majority of the patients (84.84%) have Road traffic accident as the mode of injury followed by fall from height.

Table 4: Side of Injury

Side	No. of cases	Percentage
Right	20	60.6%
Left	13	39.39%
Total	33	

In this study, right leg (60.6%) is affected more than left leg (39.39%) (Right > left).

Table 5: Clinical Type of Fracture

Types	No. of cases	Percentage
Closed	23	69.69%
Open	10	30.3%
Total	33	

The study had more number of closed (69.69%) cases than open cases.

Table 6: Schatzker's Type of Fracture

Schatzker's type	No. of cases	Percentage
I	01	3.30%
II	02	6.06%
III	00	0.00%
IV	04	12.12%
V	06	18.18%
VI	20	60.06%
Total	33	

Majority of the patients were classified under Schatzker's type VI (60.06%) followed by type V (18.18%).

Table 7: Mode of Fracture Stabilisation

Schatzker's type	JESS	Plating
I	00	01
II	00	02
III	00	00
IV	02	02
V	03	03
VI	05	15
Total	10	23

Out of total 33 patients, 10 were managed by JESS fixation and 23 by Plate fixation.

Table 8: Time to Weight Bearing

Mode of stabilization	Average time (weeks)
JESS	15.4 weeks
Plating	17.8 weeks

The study reveals that patients managed by JESS fixation had earlier weight bearing time (15.4 weeks) than those managed by Plate fixation (17.8 weeks).

Table 9:

JESS group Rasmussen Knee Score					
Duration	2 weeks	6 weeks	3 months	6 months	Latest follow up
Mean	14.7	17.2	20.8	22.1	22.5
SD	0.674	1.135	1.932	1.37	1.715

In our study on Rasmussen scoring in JESS fixation group (10 cases) we found excellent results in 0 cases, good results in 3 cases, fair results in 7 cases, and poor results in 0 cases.

Table 10:

PLATING group Rasmussen Knee Score					
Duration	2 weeks	6 weeks	3 months	6 months	Latest follow-up
Mean	17.04	19.56	21.34	22.91	24.08
SD	1.106	1.308	1.584	1.345	1.806

In our study on the basis of Rasmussen scoring in plate fixation group (23 cases) we found excellent results in 0 cases, good results in 17 cases, fair results in 6 cases, and poor results in 0 cases.

Table 11: Difference in Knee score in JESS group with time

Time	No. of patients	mean	SD	t value	p value	Inference
2 weeks	10	14.7	0.674			
6 weeks	10	17.2	1.135	10.7	<0.001	Highly significant
3 months	10	20.8	1.932	11.5	<0.001	Highly significant
6 months	10	22.1	1.37	18.97	<0.001	Highly significant
Latest follow-up	10	22.5	1.715	16.83	<0.001	Highly significant

Table 12: Difference in Knee score in PLATING group with time

Time	No. of patients	Mean	SD	t value	p value	Inference
2 weeks	23	17.04	1.106			
6 weeks	23	19.56	1.308	20.03	<0.001	Highly significant
3 months	23	21.34	1.584	23.18	<0.001	Highly significant
6 months	23	22.91	1.345	44.32	<0.001	Highly significant
Latest follow-up	23	24.08	1.806	28.96	<0.001	Highly significant

Table 13: Difference in Knee score comparison in JESS and PLATING groups

Time	JESS group			PLATING group			t value	p value	Inference
	No. of patients	Mean	SD	No. of patients	Mean	SD			
2 weeks	10	14.7	0.674	23	17.04	1.106	6.212	<0.0001	Significant
6 weeks	10	17.2	1.135	23	19.56	1.308	4.971	<0.0001	Significant
3 months	10	20.8	1.932	23	21.34	1.584	0.974	>0.05	Non-significant
6 months	10	22.1	1.37	23	22.91	1.345	1.58	>0.05	Non-significant
Latest follow-up	10	22.5	1.715	23	24.08	1.806	2.31	<0.05	Significant

Comparative analysis of the two groups at 2 weeks and 6 weeks, there is significant relationship at p value<0.001. At the period of 3 month and 6 months, both the groups were equally effective and there is non-significant relationship at the p value of >0.05. While at the latest follow-up, both the groups were significant at p value of <0.001.

Clinical assessment.

Pain	
None	6
Occasional	5
Stabbing pain in certain position	3
Constant pain after activity	1
Significant rest pain	-3
Walking capacity	
Normal walking capacity for age	6
Walking outdoors more than one hour	5
Walking outdoor 15 mins – 1 hour	3
Walking outdoor <15 mins	1
Walking indoor only	0
Knee extension	
Lack of extension <10°	2
Lack of extension >10°	0
Lack of extension >20°	-2
Total range of motion	
Full	6
At least 120°	5
At least 90°	3
At least 60°	1
<60°	-3
Stability	
Normal stability in extension and 20° flexion	6
Abnormal instability in 20° flexion	4
Instability in extension <10°	2
Instability in extension >10°	0
Power of quadriceps	
Grade 5	2
Grade 3-4	1
Grade <3	-2
Maximum score	
Excellent	28-30
Good	24-27
Fair	20-23
Poor	<20

Figure 1: Modified Rasmussen's score – clinical assessment

Case No. 1:

Mr. Sa; 35y/M, DOI: 28/11/2019 MOI: Fall from scooty

Figure 2:

Follow-up (10 months)

Figure 3:

Range of motion at latest follow-up

Knee flexion

Knee extension

Squatting

Cross-legged sitting

Figure 4:

Case No. 2

Mr. As; 45y/M, DOI: 6/3/2021, MOI: Fall in pit on road

Figure 5:

Range of motion at latest follow-up

Figure 6:

Discussion: A total of 33 patients of Intra-articular fracture of proximal tibia were included in this study, categorized by Schatzker's classification and were followed up for a minimum period of 6

months. This was similar to the study by Biswas et al (2014) [3], Herode et al (2016) [4] but contrasted with studies by Z Yu et al (2009) [5], CC Chan et al (2012) [6], Shah et al (2017) [7].

Table 14:

Study	Sample size	Classification used
Biswas et al (2014) [3]	30	Schatzker's
Harpreet Singh et al (2015) [8]	20	Schatzker's
Herode et al (2016) [4]	50	Schatzker's
Dwivedi A et al [24]	36	Schatzker's
Huda N et al [25]	50	Schatzker's
	Sample size	Classification used
Yu Z et al (2009) [5]	65	AO
CC Chan et al (2012) [6]	82	AO
Shah et al (2017) [7]	70	AO

In our study 23 patients were treated by plate fixation and 10 patients were managed by JESS fixation. Studies with similar and contrasting treatment modalities are as in below table.

Table 15:

Study	Treatment Modality
Herode et al (2016) [4]	Various modalities (Canulated cancelous screw, Buttress plating, locked compression plate)
Yu Z et al (2009) [5]	Double buttress plating
Ramesh Chand et al (2015) [9]	Intramedullary Nailing versus Proximal tibia plating
Sunil Kumar et al (2014)[10]	JESS
Harpreet Singh et al (2015) [8]	JESS
CC Chan et al (2012) [6]	Hybrid External fixation versus Internal fixation
Dwivedi A et al [24]	Plate osteosynthesis versus JESS
Huda N et al [25]	Plate osteosynthesis versus JESS

In our study patients were clinically assessed by modified Rasmussen score for functional assessment at regular intervals (2 weeks, 3 months, 6 months) for minimum period of 6 months. This was similar to the study by CC Chan et al (2012) [6], Biswas et al (2014) [3], Herode et al (2016) [4], Shah et al (2017) [7]. However, certain studies assessed the outcome by different scoring variable too.

Table 16:

Study	Outcome variable
CC Chan et al (2012) [6]	Rasmussen score
Biswas et al (2014) [3]	
Herode et al (2016) [4]	
Shah et al (2017) [7]	
Patel et al (2017) [11]	Knee society score (KSS)
Harpreet Singh et al (2015) [8]	
Dwivedi A et al [24]	Knee society score (KSS)
Sunil Kumar et al (2014) [10]	Rick / Delamertier & Mason Hohl score
Yu Z et al (2009) [5]	HSS score, Lysholm score, Knee Society Clinical Rating Score
Huda N et al [25]	Modified Rasmussen's functional score

Majority of the patients in our study (84.84%) have road traffic accident (especially two-wheelers) as the mode of injury with mean age of 35.72 years. This can be explained, as in these age group activities of livelihood, job opportunities and

vehicular mobility predispose them to high energy vehicular accidents. This was consistent with the study by Sreenath Rao et al (2018) [12], Herode et al (2016) [4], Cole PA et al (2004) [13], Ricci WM et al (2004) [14] and Stannard JP et al (2003) [15]

Table 17:

study	Mean age
Sreenath Rao et al (2018) [12]	37.75 years
Herode et al (2016) [4]	38.50 years
Cole PA et al (2004) [13]	35 years

Ricci WM et al (2004) [14]	40 years
Stannard JP et al (2003) [15]	37 years
Dwivedi A et al [24]	47 years

Table 18:

study	Mode of injury
Sreenath Rao et al (2018) [12]	85% RTA
Herode et al (2016) [4]	73.3% RTA

In our study, we found males are affected more (87.8%) as compared to females (12.2%). The reason could be males being the earning member of the family causing the need to travel more, thereby increasing the chances of accidents. This was consistent with the study by Herode et al (2016) [4], Biswas et al (2016) [3], Lee et al (2007) [16], Albuquerque et al (2013) [17].

Table 19:

Herode et al (2016) [4]	80% males
Biswas et al (2016) [3]	70% males
Albuquerque et al (2013) [17]	70.3% males
Lee et al (2007) [16]	65.71% males

Our study had incidence of right leg involved in 60.6% of the cases compared to left leg involved in 39.39% cases. This was consistent with studies by Herode et al (2016) [4], Patel et al (2017) [11] and contrasted with study by Shah et al (2017) [7].

Table 20:

Herode et al (2016) [4]	60% right leg
Patel et al (2017) [11]	70% right leg
Shah et al (2017)[17]	53.6% left leg

Out of the 33 cases in our study, 23 cases were closed fracture and rest 10 were open fractures based on Gustilo-Anderson typing similar to study by Shah et al (2017) [17].

Majority of fractures were Schatzker's type VI (57.57%) followed by type V (18.18%) which was similar to study by Yu Z et al (2009) [5] and Ruslan GS et al (1998) [18]. The mean full weight bearing time in Plating group was 17.8 weeks similar to study by Yu Z et al (2009) [5] of 18.7 weeks weight bearing time. The mean modified Rasmussen score for JESS fixation was 22.5 and Plate fixation was 24.08 which correlated well with study of Hitin Mathur et al (2005) [19] with mean functional score of 25.062.

Complications: Although standard techniques of open reduction and internal fixation have proven to be routinely successful in restoring the osseous anatomy, the tenuous soft tissue coverage and predilection for high energy trauma of proximal tibia has substantial rate of complications too. The major problem faced by us during the study was Knee stiffness in 3 cases due to prolonged immobilization. Pin tract infection in 2 cases of JESS fixation and surgical site infection in 2 cases of Plate fixation with 1 leading to wound dehiscence and other resolving on regular dressing and intravenous antibiotic administration. There was 1 case of neuropraxic nerve injury which recovered in subsequent follow-up.

Table 21:

Study	Complication
Herode et al (2016) [4]	Infection(n=1), Knee stiffness(n=1)
Shah et al (2017) [7]	Infection(n=3), Malunion(n=6)
Patel et al(2017) [11]	Infection(n=2)
Harpreet Singh et al (2015) [8]	Pin tract infection(n=2), Nonunion(n=1)
Sunil Kumar et al (2014) [10]	Pin tract infection(n=7), Nonunion(n=1)
Huda N et al [25]	Superficial infection in 2 (8.0%) patients in Plating group and 6 (24.0%) patients in JESS group

According to a study by Uhl et al (2008) [20], the primary aim is to protect soft tissue and there were high complication rates due to the amount of soft tissue dissection needed to adequately expose the fracture site for open reduction, as it devitalizes the

comminuted bone fragments. Reports by Young and Barrack [21], Moore et al (1987) [22], and Mallik et al (1992) [23] highlighted the risks of conventional plate fixation due to tenuous soft-tissue coverage. In our study minimally invasive

percutaneous reduction techniques have been favoured for both plating and JESS. In our study JESS being minimally invasive, caused less wound related complications and early mobilization (15.4 weeks for JESS and 17.8 weeks for plating), but had poor reduction of fragments in severe grade fractures. No problem in fracture union was reported in our series.

Summary

In our study in JESS fixation, there is less risk of soft tissue complications, also early mobilization of joint was possible decreasing chances of knee stiffness. Patients managed by JESS fixation also had earlier weight bearing than those managed by Plate fixation. However, in plate fixation, the articular congruity was maintained better due to open reduction.

In our study overall final outcome was better in plate fixation method ($p < 0.05$) this is similar with study done by Dwivedi et al [24] and they also reported earlier bone consolidation in plate fixation group. Our results are in contrast with Huda N et al [25] where JESS fixation group has better outcome than plating group having type I fracture among 10 (20.0%), type II among 15 (30.0%), type IV among 2 (4.0%), type V among 10 (20.0%), and type VI among 13 (26.0%) patients.

Conclusion

Plate fixation is the method in most of the intra-articular fractures. Plate fixation due to maintenance of articular congruity gives finally better functional outcome in some studies as found in study by Dwivedi et al [24]. JESS external fixation is also an effective method in treating low grade intra-articular fractures by closed means and results in early joint mobilization. In our study total 60% cases were schatzker's type VI and 18.18% were schatzker's type V, results showed better functional outcome in plate fixation as compared to JESS fixation. Our study had some limitations. First, we had to include patients of wide age group and mainly have type VI and type V of Schatzker's fractures. Second, the absence of long-term follow-up to evaluate the outcome of malalignment in terms of the development of osteoarthritis of the knee.

Bibliography

1. Skinner HB. Current diagnosis and treatment in orthopaedics. 2nd Ed. New York: McGraw Hill Inc; 2000. pp. 110-111.
2. Hohl M. Articular fractures of the proximal tibia. In: Everts CM, editor. Surgery of the musculoskeletal system. New York: Churchill-Livingstone; 1993. p. 3471-97.
3. Biswas SK, Puri SR, Salgia A, Sanghi S, Mir F, Mehta R. Management of the proximal tibia fractures by mini external fixation: A case series of 30 cases. Medical Journal of Dr. DY Patil University. 2014 Jan 1; 7(1):36.

4. Herode P, Shroff A, Patel JM, Sadaria MH, Hurkat H. Comparison of Outcome of Various Modalities of Treatment of Tibia Plateau Fractures. Orthopedic Research and Reviews. 2016 Oct 7; 1(1).
5. Yu Z, Zheng L, Zhang Y, Li J, Ma B. Functional and radiological evaluations of high-energy tibial plateau fractures treated with double-buttress plate fixation. European journal of medical research. 2009 Dec; 14(5):200-5.
6. Chan CC, Keating J. Comparison of outcomes of operatively treated bicondylar tibial plateau fractures by external fixation and internal fixation. Malaysian orthopaedic journal. 2012 Mar; 6(1):7.
7. Dr. Smit Shah, Dr. Pulkit Maniar, Dr. Niravkumar Moradiya. Management of fractures of proximal tibia by various treatment modalities: A study of 56 patients. Int J Orthop Sci 2017; 3(1):346-350. DOI: 10.22271/ortho.2017.v3.i1f.51
8. Singh H, Misra RK, Kaur M. Management of proximal tibia fractures using wire based circular external fixator. Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR. 2015 Sep; 9(9):RC01.
9. Meena RC, Meena UK, Gupta GL, Gahlot N, Gaba S. Intramedullary nailing versus proximal plating in the management of closed extra-articular proximal tibial fracture: a randomized controlled trial. Journal of Orthopaedics and Traumatology. 2015 Sep; 16(3):203-8.
10. Sunil Kumar, Dinesh Kumar, Surendra Kumar, Anil Srivastava: A Prospective analysis of the efficacy of JESS (Joshi's External Stabilizing System) fixator in management of complex tibial plateau fractures. IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences (IOSR -JDMMS) e ISSN: 2279 0853, p - ISSN: 2279 - 0861 Volume 13, Issue 7 Ver. V (July 2014), PP 45-52.
11. Patel M, Sharma J, Jakhar S. Functional outcome of dual plate osteosynthesis in type V and VI Proximal tibial fracture. Indian J Orthop Surg. 2017; 3(1):78-83.
12. Jakinapally SR, Konuganti SR, Rao VP, Rapur S. Functional and radiological evaluation of surgical management in tibial plateau fractures: a prospective study. International Journal of Research in Orthopaedics. 2018 Mar; 4(2):261.
13. Cole PA, Zlowodzki M, Kregor PJ. Treatment of proximal tibia fractures using the less invasive stabilization system: surgical experience and early clinical results in 77 fractures. Journal of orthopaedic trauma. 2004 Sep 1; 18(8):528-35.

14. Ricci WM, Rudzki JR, Borrelli Jr J. Treatment of complex proximal tibia fractures with the less invasive skeletal stabilization system. *Journal of orthopaedic trauma*. 2004 Sep 1; 18(8):521-7.
15. Stannard JP, Wilson TC, Volgas DA, Alonso JE. Fracture stabilization of proximal tibial fractures with the proximal tibial LISS: early experience in Birmingham, Alabama (USA). *Injury*. 2003 Aug 1; 34:S36-42.
16. Lee JA, Papadakis SA, Moon C, Zalavras CG. Tibial plateau fractures treated with the less invasive stabilisation system. *International orthopaedics*. 2007 Jun; 31(3):415-8.
17. Albuquerque RP, Hara R, Prado J, Schiavo L, Giordano V, Amaral NP. Estudo epidemiológico das fraturas do planalto tibial em Hospital de Trauma nível I. *Acta Ortopédica Brasileira*. 2013; 21:109-15.
18. Ruslan GS, Razak M. The results of surgical treatment of tibial plateau fractures. *The Medical journal of Malaysia*. 1998 Sep 1; 53:35-41.
19. Mathur, Hitin & Acharya, Shankar & Nijhawan, VK & Mandal, SP. (2005). Operative results of closed tibial plateau fractures. *Indian Journal of Orthopaedics*. 39. 10.4103/0019-5413.36784.
20. Uhl RL, Gainor J, Horning J. Treatment of bicondylar tibial plateau fractures with lateral locking plates. *Orthopedics (Online)*. 2008 May 1; 31(5):473.
21. Young M, Barrack RL. Complications of internal fixation of tibial plateau fractures. *Orthopaedic review*. 1994 Feb 1; 23(2):149-54.
22. Moore TM, Patzakis MJ, Harvey JP. Tibial plateau fractures: definition, demographics, treatment rationale, and long-term results of closed traction management or operative reduction. *Journal of orthopaedic trauma*. 1987 Jan 1; 1(2):97-119.
23. Mallik AR, Covall DJ, Whitelaw GP. Internal versus external fixation of bicondylar tibial plateau fractures. *Orthopaedic review*. 1992 Dec 1; 21(12):1433-6.
24. Dwivedi A, Sharma A, Ashta V, Nairobi R, Nandi S. Comparative analysis between locking compression plate and Joshi's external stabilization system in the management of proximal tibial fractures. *Int J Res Orthop* 2021; 7:56-61.
25. Huda N, Bishnoi S, Shahid M, Keshav K, Altaf D, Kumar K. Joshi's external stabilization system versus locked compression plating in the management of tibial plateau fractures: A nonrandomized prospective study. *J Bone Joint Dis* 2021; 36:14-20.